

A new update on the Cadomian paleoreconstruction of the Iberian Gondwana margin: the Sierra Albarrana metasedimentary group

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The Sierra Albarrana Group is exposed right to the S of the Badajoz-Córdoba Shear Zone (Ossa-Morena Complex; Díez Fernández & Arenas 2015), resting under the Central Unit and conforming a SW autochthonous section of the Variscan Orogen. The main lithologies are metasedimentary rocks and minor metabasites folded into an antiformal structure, and distributed into mainly four lithostratigraphic successions. These successions display dominantly siliciclastic features with Early Paleozoic age (Solis-Alulima et al. 2022), from bottom to top, Albarrana Succession, Cabril-Peña Grajera Succession, Albariza-Bembézar Succession, and Azuaga Fm. (González del Tánago & Peinado 1990). Feldspathic quartzites, paragneisses, metapelites, and thin-bedded slates correspond respectively to the most frequent lithological groups in these four successions. A detailed geochemical and Nd-isotope study of these rocks may be of interest in order to determinate the primary location of their sedimentary paleobasins along the peri-Gondwanan margin where they were deposited during Cambrian times.

Geochemical compositions of the metasedimentary rock successions in Sierra Albarrana Group place the deposition under the influence of a peri-Gondwanan active margin in a probable evolution to a passive margin (Fuenlabrada et al. 2021). Geochemical features suggest sedimentary maturity and recycled materials dominantly from reworked continental upper crustal sources with dominant felsic contributions. Negative $\epsilon\text{Nd}_{(530)}$ (ranging from 11.3 to 4.5), and old Nd model ages (TDM: 1388–1897 Ma) imply reworked materials from old continental source areas with a limited contribution from juvenile sources. These geochemical and isotope features are in agreement with the progressive denudation of rocks bearing the isotopic imprint from an old Paleoproterozoic basement exposed along the Gondwanan margin, where their paleobasins probably occupied an outboard position across this margin during Cambrian times. Nd model ages of the Sierra Albarrana Group (Fuenlabrada et al. 2021) overlap those found in the Early Cambrian series from the southernmost Central Iberian Zone (TDM: 1444–1657 Ma; Fuenlabrada et al. 2016), sharing common geochemical features that locate both sedimentary basins during Cambrian times in a relatively close section of the Gondwanan margin, within a comparable geodynamic scenario. This geochemical and isotope features allow to locate the sedimentary basins of the Sierra Albarrana successions within a previous model of the peri-Gondwanan margin (Fuenlabrada et al. 2020) for Ediacaran-Cambrian times, occupying an eastern lateral position along the Gondwanan margin, closer to the Tuareg Shield and the Sahara Metacraton (Fig. 1), which provided abundant Paleoproterozoic and Archean detrital materials.

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Figure 1. Schematic paleogeographic reconstruction model (not to scale) for the Gondwanan margin during the approximate Ediacaran–Cambrian transition (c. 540 Ma) (Fuenlabrada et al. 2021). Iberian sedimentary basins locations are shown in relation to the main North African cratonic masses. CIZ—Central Iberian Zone. OMC (Ossa-Morena Complex), AM (Armorican Massif), and SXTZ (Saxo-Thuringian Zone) locations according to Rojo-Pérez et al. (2021). Arrows show the probable provenance for the detrital materials.
